

WORD ORDER IN KARONESE LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The problem of this research was finding the word order in *Karonese* Language. The research used qualitative to find the data. The data was taken from the native speakers from *Karonese* language. The instrument of this research was observation and interview. The result of this research was found that the most word order of *Karonese* language is VSO/PSO. The conclusions obtained from the data above are that Word orders contained in *Karonese* were SPO, VOS / POS, VSO / PSO, and OSV / OSP. In addition to regular sentences, there are also clause sentences in which the word order was in the form of VSO while compound sentences were equivalent to the word order in the form of S-P.

Keywords: word order, *Karonese*, language

1. Introduction

Word orders are needed in forming a sentence. Of course the sentence arranged using word order will develop into the language used by every culture in the world. Comrie (1989: 86) adds that typological grammar sequences played an important role in language development. This was confirmed by Greenberg in his writing which discussed the typology of the order of grammar. His research not only addresses universal language and typology, but how it is used. Comrie (1989: 86) grouped six word orders in a sentence. The six word orders are SOV, SVO, VSO, VOS, OVS, and OSV. See the formation of word orders in the sentence below:

- | | | |
|-----------------------|-----|--------------|
| 1) Hasan buffalo buy | SOV | (Turki) |
| 2) Hasan buys buffalo | SVO | (English) |
| 3) Buy Hasan buffalo | VSO | (Welsh) |
| 4) Buy buffalo Hasan | VOS | (Malagasy) |
| 5) Buffalo buy Hasan | OVS | (Hixkaryana) |
| 6) Buffalo Hasan buy | OSV | (Aurina) |

Dominantly, *Karonese* language Predicate – Subject, except active language, Woolams (2004:382). Berikut tipe word order dalam bahasa Karo:

- | | | |
|--------|-----------------------|----------------------|
| 1) SVO | <i>Ia napui rumah</i> | She sweep the house. |
| 2) SOV | <i>Ia rumah napui</i> | She the house sweep. |

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- | | | |
|--------|-----------------------|----------------------|
| 3) VSO | <i>Napui ia rumah</i> | sweep she house. |
| 4) VOS | <i>Napui rumah ia</i> | sweep the house she. |
| 5) OVS | <i>Rumah napui ia</i> | The house sweep she. |
| 6) OSV | <i>Rumah ia napui</i> | The house she sweep. |

Word order *Karonesse* which is dominantly appears is VSO / PSO type because *Karonesse* language is generally a passive sentence which P is at the beginning of a sentence and the subject is a noun. Followed by SVO / SPO. Word orders that will be examined in this study are word orders which are classified based on syntactic typologies.

There some articles that had the same topic with the research. They were *Tipologi Bahasa Karo* (Surbakti 2012), *Tata Bahasa Karo* (Woollams, 2004), dan *Fenomena Tipologi Gramatikal Bahasa Minangkabau: Akusatif, Ergatif, atau Campur* (Jufrizal: 2008)

2. Method

The method of this research would be used in the research is qualitative methods. Qualitative methods are an easy method when dealing with multiple realities. This method presents the nature of the relationship between informants and researchers directly (Moleong: 2004). The approach used to the subject of this research is the language typology approach because the object of research was *Karonesse* native speakers. Meanwhile the technique used in the research was observing and interviewing by recording directly.

3. Result Finding and Discussion

The result finding of this research would be elaborate below based on word order in *Karonesse* sentence.

3.1 Word order Based on (S-P-O) Subject-Predicate-Object

No.	Karonesse Language	Glosary
1.	<i>Si Terbeluh lalap maba ranan</i> S (Frek) P O	Terbeluh was warming up the conversation.
2.	<i>Mehamat kuskas ndarami nakan man pangan.</i> S P O	Mehamat was busy finding the food.
3.	<i>Mama ras kela paksana erban sumur.</i> S P O	Uncle and brother in law was digging the well.
4.	<i>Ise pe la meteh perjabun sumbang.</i> S P O	Noone know their marriage as blood
5.	<i>Aku rusur nampati nandeku erdakan.</i> S P O	I always help my mother cook.
6.	<i>Ceda ate naring ngiani pusuhku.</i> S P O	Only disappointment is in my heart.
7.	<i>Bolang peberkat kempuna ku Tiga Juhar.</i> S P O	Grandpa sent his grandson to Tiga Juhar
8.	<i>Peganci-ganci kami erbahanca ras njabab sa</i> S P O	Taking turns we made him answer.
9.	<i>Nande mereken bangku sen.</i>	Mother gives me money.

	S P O	
10.	<i>Aku nimai denga surat i Kantor Pos nari</i>	I am waiting for letter from post office.
	S P O	

In the active sentence above (1, 2, 3 and 4) there were three constituents with the arrangement of subjects, predicates and objects. Other constituents could also be raised among these core constituents. For example adverbs that express frequency or how to do, additional information or negation can be used between subjects and predicates.

Predicates in sentences number 5, 6, 7, and 8 were played by transitive active verbs. These transitive active verbs typically begun with inflectional in the form of a prefix 'n unless the verb is derived through the use of the transitive prefix *pe-* or *per-*. In addition to these types of verbs, the only other exponent for the predicate in the active sentence was in the form of irregular verbs (causes) which, although judging from the form are classified as intransitive verbs, but from all other aspects are actually considered transitive .

While sentences number 9 and 10 are predicates and objects are separated by prepositional phrases or *adenga* help words (still) if the object is longer than usual. All active sentences in Karo are ransparent, ie there are no active sentences found with multiple objects (one direct object, one indirect object) in the use of this language.

3.2 Word order Based on (VOS/POS) Predicate- Object-Subject

This sentence arrangement was used if the object is played by the pronoun *kai* (what) or *ise* (who) in accordance with the general principle that this question word should be placed as close as possible to the initial position of the sentence. The sentence arrangement on numbers 3, 4 and 5 was used if the object is played by a noun that is used non-referent.

No.	Karonese Language	Glosary
1.	<i>Nukur kai kam ku tiga?</i> P O S	What do you buy to market?
2.	<i>Ndahi ise kam ku Tiga?</i> P O S	Who do you visit to market?
3.	<i>Ngelegi lau aku.</i> P O S	I take water.
4.	<i>Maba barang aku ku tiga.</i> P O S	Bring goods I to market.
5.	<i>Medil perik bapa.</i> P O S	Shooting bird father.

In each of the examples above, nouns that portray objects refer only to a type of object that is intended in general (non-referent) and did not refer to a particular number of nouns of the type of noun. According to the semantic aspect, the object in the sentence was actually included in the predicate. It was true that when viewed from the functional, such sentences were classified as intransitive sentences. The object of this sentence showed that to be non-referential because such objects cannot be changed using adjectives.

in final intonation, while in the declarative sentence, the intonation decreases. In interrogative sentences it was common to find an interrogative particle located right after the predicate. This interrogative particle gave a subtle but important difference to the expectations of the speaker.

Example:

Beltu-beltu kai kin e? (S-V/S-P).

'*beltu-beltu* how this *kin*'

Kin, that is, particles which indicate that the speaker was expecting the question to tend to answer positively. Interrogative Conclusions: Sentences Ask "yes / no" almost all have VS / PS arrangements in the Question content sentence, the question word generally appears as close as possible at the beginning of the sentence, while the intransitive sentence containing the question word experiences an almost all arrangement SV / SV.

3.4.3. Word order in Imperative Sentence

Imperative in Karonese language, especially the context of the recording sentence was addressed to the other person who is understood from the context, usually not expressed in sentences.

Example:

(1) *Uat kalender nen wari, piga berngi bulan!*

'take the calendar look at the day, how many nights and months.'

(2) *tama ku para tuhur!*

'put to the *para tuhur* (the storied people above the stove)'

The imperative in the Karonese language is also marked by the word 'enda', a marker of imperative requests or requests. Example: You can honestly suck me here! Orkan I offer cigarettes to grandma (ancestor) 'The imperative in this recording also has an ending -a marker to express urgency or hope for a desire. Example: *Caburen* basement *cabur* is my search! 'Star studded in the sky, more scattered my fortune'.

3.5 Word Order in Clause

Surbakti (2012:62) found syntactic typologies based on grammar (word order). The typology of *Karonese* based on word order is:

3.5.1 Sentence Based on Clause

1) Singular Sentence

1.1 *Tersinget-singet ruluh niding enda.* (PSO)

P S O

'by the way this *niding* was luck'

1.2 *Labo nen wari niding enda?* (PSO)

Must *niding* look the day ?'

1.3 *Waja melala atendu perbalok gajah kuning nge teman.*(OSP)

'Bait a lot, the name is also the yellow elephant friend's bandage'

from the data above, could be concluded that the singular sentence was V-S/P-S and it was followed by S-V/S-P.

2) Compound Sentence

2.1 Multilevel Compound Sentence

2.1.1 *Adi lit kalender nen adi lalit lang. (P)*

'Look If there was a calendar, ignore if there was not.'

From the compound sentence of '*adi*' was the Dari kalimat majemuk bertingkat di atas *adi* adalah Characteristics of condition markers.

2.1.2 *Bangku kerina dahin ndai, sebab aku ngenca ngangkasa.*

S S P

'All the responsibility was given for me because I understand it.'

2.1.3 *Adi ijenda kin ia tading, simehulina bereken man ia gupak enda.*

K P O

'If he lives here it is better the knife is given for him'

'*Adi*' in sentence above was the complement character and if it written in the first sentence so it will be a clause develop of complement. The basic pattern of the developing complement used '*adi*' geberally used K-P and K-P-S.

2.1.4 *Si mejinna pe rupana labo dalih gelah ngit ertanggung jawab. (+)*

S P O

'Ugly face is not problem the important thing is his responsibility'

2.1.5 *Si kertang-kertangna pe labo dalih gelah mbue tabeh-tabehna (+)*

S P O

'The thin size is not problem the poin is patty'

From the two examples above, it found that multilevel compound sentence markers were distinguished from the use of the 'who'. Internally, these clauses had a basic structure of clauses except if the position of the subject prefix in this clause was replaced by the relative character of the subject that is replaced with the main noun explained by the clause.

3) The Equivalent Sentence

3.1 *Soalna sangket ia je enggoh, saja ola nen. (+)*

S P
P-S-K K-P

'The problem is stuck there, but don't see it often'

3.2 *Berarti niding enda ras njala enggo seri kap warina e? (+)*

S P

'Means that this is *niding* and the date is the same as the day?'

3.3 *Cabur bintang bas langit, caburen lah pencarinku (+)*

S P
P S K P S O

'star-studded in the sky, my fortune is more scattered'

The sentence was conected two clauses that had two pattern. The basic pattern of equivalent sentence was subject and predicate.

3.5.2 Word Order Based on Active and Pasive

1) Active Sentence

1.1 *Buatken kalender* (PS)

P S

Nenken wari kai sendah! (PS)

P S

'Take the calendar what day is today.'

1.2 *Buat kari nakanku si datas eja ena* (PS)

P S

'Take my meal on the table'

From the active sentence above the dominant word order was subject and predicate. There were two constituent in Karonese sentence and the pattern was subject and predicate and others subject –predicate-object . Another constituent could be found in the poin of the sentence. For example the complement that expressed the frequency, the addition complement between subject and predicate.

1.3 *Enda kududurken bandu isapku* (SPOO)

S P O O

'I give my cigarette for you'

The finding of the example above could be seen that the type of active sentence also has an S-P-O pattern which was two sentences that have the same pattern but different types of objects. The active sentence of O-co-sufferers S-V-O and patient's O-co-active sentence. This sentence occured because this sentence is an imperative sentence in the form of a very expected request and usually the word honesty is for the creator or *kalimbubu* (*Dibata idah* (God in sight) in *Karonese* customs. -time when viewed from different contexts the sentence can also be called a positive declarative sentence.

2) Pasive Sentence

The passive sentence of the *Karonese* language contains at least two types of constituents in general, namely P-S or V-S. The subject of passive sentences was typically played by a noun phrase and has a semantic role as a sufferer. Predicates were generally phrases containing a compulsory central element played by a passive verb coupled with complementary non-compulsory actors played by certain types of noun phrases that have semantic roles as actors.

Example:

2.1 *Tersinget-singet ruluh niding enda.* (PSO)

P S O

Remember this niding again

2.2 *La mbue bas ia tabas.*(KSP)

The spell was not much.

2.3 *Enggom bene sie kerina.*(PSO)

Has lost all.

Generally, the pattern of VSO or PSO in *Karonese* 'niding' was passive sentence but it was not absolute, both in interogative and declarative.

4. Recommendation

This reseach hopefully can give contribution to the further researcher expecially for Karonese culture. The problem is most of the researchers from Karonese language is hard to find the references that the topic related to Karonese language. Finally the government of Karonese can help the researcher to develop their reserach so it can be useful for linguistics students.

5. Conclusion

The conclusions of this research can be concluded that the pattern of Word orders in *Karonese* were SPO, VOS / POS, VSO / PSO and OSV / OSP. In addition to regular sentences, there were also clause sentences in which the word order is in the form of VSO while compound sentences were equivalent to the word order in the form of S-P. At the end of the discovery of the data obtained active and passive sentences. Word order contained in the active sentence *Karonese* language was P-S and word order in passive sentences is SPO. The subject of passive sentences was typically played by a noun phrase and has a semantic role as a sufferer. Predicates were generally phrases containing a compulsory central element played by a passive verb coupled with complementary non-compulsory actors played by certain types of noun phrases that have semantic roles as actors.

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References

- Comrie, Bernard. 1988. *Linguistik Tipology* dalam F.J. Newmeyer (ed) *Linguistic: The Cambridge Survey*. Vol. 1 Hal 447-467. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Comrie, Bernard. 1983, 1989. *Language Unioersals and Linguistik Tipology*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell Publisher Limited.
- Moleong. 2004. *Metode Kualitatif*. Bandung: Rosdakarya.

- Surbakti, Ernawati. 2012. *Tipologi Sintaksis Bahasa Karo*. Jurnal Telangkai Bahasa dan Sastra, Januari 2012, 55-73. Tahun 6 Volume 1. USU.
- Juprizal. 2008. *Fenomena Tipologi Gramatikal Bahasa Minangkabau: Akusatif, Ergatif, atau Campur*. Universitas Udayana Bali: Jurnal Linguistika Vol 15, No. 28, Maret 2008.
- Woollams, Geoff. 2004. *Tata Bahasa Karo*. Medan: Bina Media Perintis.

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